

A Conversation of Rumors: Indian Subalterns' Strategy for Micro-Political Struggle

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Abstract:

Rumor is the enabling mode of protest for Indian peasant subalterns, making it possible for them to transmit their messages with an ease and rapidity that the ruling classes often found bewildering, thus avoiding individual responsibility. The analysis of four Indian novels written in English, *The Village*, *Kanthapura*, *Cradle of the Clouds* and *A Suitable Boy*, which spans from 1920s to 1960s, when the Indian nationalist movement, the land reform and modernization after Indian independence were in full swing, makes it clear that rumor makes the peasant subalterns the subject of history with their own

distinctive forms of consciousness and making sense of and acting upon the world on its own terms.

Keywords: rumor, peasant subaltern, *The Village*, *Kanthapura*, *Cradle of the Clouds*, *A Suitable Boy*

Introduction

Contemporary India is characterized by electoral democracy, fast economic growth, yet a huge gap between the rich and the poor, urban areas and villages. Historically, the process of industrialization in all agrarian countries has meant the eviction of peasants from the land, either because the land was taken over for urban or industrial development or because the peasant no longer had the means to cultivate the land. Besides, market forces were usually strong enough to force peasants to give up the land. Large sections of peasants who are today the victims of the primitive accumulation of capital are completely unlikely to be absorbed into the new capitalist sectors of growth (Chatterjee, 2010, p. 196). However, the Indian government is obliged to reverse the consequences of primitive accumulation for more votes. Therefore, it provides alternative means of livelihood by offering easy loans to enable those without the means of sustenance to find some

gainful employment, and offers some direct benefits, such as direct delivery of subsidized or free food, to people who, because of poverty or other reasons, are unable to meet their basic consumption needs.

Nowadays, we can see that the Indian poor open up a space named "political society" (Chatterjee, 2004, p. 27) by Indian political theorist Partha Chatterjee. Different from civil society, which emphasizes citizenship and rights, represents elite groups, communities, civic freedom, reason and law, political society is the site of negotiation and dispute developed by the government targeting at the governed population (Chatterjee, 2004, p. 52), namely, the process in which the urban poor living in slums and shanty town struggle for government's compromise for more welfare. However, in the annual Global Hunger Index report jointly released by two European non-governmental organizations on October 15th, India, which managed to rank fifth in the world in terms of GDP growth, ranked 107th

out of 121 countries listed in the report. According to the World Bank, 80 percent of the poor live in rural areas, and the highest share of poor people is among the scheduled castes¹, at about 43 percent. It can be seen that farmers, especially low-caste farmers, are excluded from the democratic government of India and cannot even enter into the space of “political society” to fight for their rights and interests.

Nevertheless, is it the truth that disadvantaged peasants – including small tenant farmers, landless farm laborers, and artisans, or we can call them “subaltern” – the term coined by Antonio Gramsci to identify groups that were excluded, displaced, and marginalized so that their political voices would be denied, and later developed by Gayatri Spivak as groups “removed from all lines of social mobility” (2005, p. 475) – have no choice but to be saved, to remain passive and subordinate? The modernists reduce peasants subaltern as backward and premodern; nationalists label them as simple and ignorant, and as an object of their strategies, to be acted upon, controlled, and appropriated within their respective structures of state power (Chatterjee, 1993, p. 158-159). They hardly realize that peasants subaltern are in fact able to make sense of the world outside their village not in terms of the discursive forms of modern bourgeois politics but rather by translating it into their own codes (Chatterjee, 1993, p. 160). Ranajit Guha, the vastly influential scholar in the Subaltern Studies group, found that many of the most important peasant insurrections in the country were largely autonomous, and that the intervention of “outside” leaders was a marginal and, often, a late phenomenon (Pandey, 1982, p. 151). The structure of peasants’ mentality is a largely unconscious logical system lying beneath the surface of myths, beliefs, values and activities. (Sarkar, 1984, p. 277) Among the six “elementary aspects” of the insurgent peasant consciousness that Guha identified, which are “negation, ambiguity, modality, solidarity,

transmission, and territoriality”, transmission is an indispensable part in constructing the collective solidarity among the poor. The message “was transmitted with an ease and rapidity that the ruling classes often found bewildering” (Chatterjee, 1993, p. 162) through characteristic channels, among which “rumor” is a crucial one.

Rumor gives peasant subalterns a collective yet anonymous voice. (Arnold, 1984, p. 87) It is a “hidden transcript” written beneath the “public transcript” (Scott, 1990. p. x), namely, the official records and history dominated by the elite bourgeois, that we can brand it as one form of “Brechtian forms of class struggle” (Scott, 1985). By phrasing their thoughts in rumors, vulnerable groups express their hidden aspirations in public in a way that both enables them to avoid individual responsibility and aligns them with some higher power whose express commands they are merely following. Such portents have, at the same time, helped fuel countless rebellions (Scott, 1990. p. 148).

The paper intends to grasp the peasant consciousness reflected in their rumors by analyzing four Indian novels written in English, namely, *The Village* (1939) written by Mulk Raj Anand, *Kanthapura* (1947) by Raja Rao, *Cradle of the Clouds* (1951) by Sudhin N. Ghose, and *A Suitable Boy* (1993) by Vikram Seth. The time in the novel spans from 1920s to 1960s, when the Indian nationalist movement, the land reform and modernization after Indian independence were in full swing. Peasant subalterns carry out their micro-political struggles through rumors. They were neither in overt collective defiance of powerholders nor in complete hegemonic compliance, but in the vast territory between these two polar opposites. The Indian subalterns today, are likely to draw on the resistance tactics from the political practices of their ancestors to fight for a better life.

¹ scheduled castes: the backward and most backward castes listed by the Governments. If a particular Dalit caste or a specific tribe is on the government list, then a person from that caste or tribe can avail the advantage of reservation.

Characterizing Rumors in Indian Village

In the classic definition formulated by the psychologists Allport and Postman, a “rumor...is a specific (or topical) proposition for belief, passed along from person to person, usually by word of mouth, without secure standards of evidence being present.” (Allport & Postman, 1947, p. ix) Considerable consensus exists in the literature, however, regarding the interpretation of rumors as a phenomenon arising in ambiguous situations and flourishing in times of social unrest and tension. Indeed, rumors emerge purposively rather than accidentally as they represent the preoccupations of a “public” seeking to comprehend the exigencies of their precarious situations. In other words, the presence of rumors in a society does not necessarily signify a breakdown in communication but an attempt at collective conversation by people who wish to enter their sentiments into a public discourse (Yang, 1987 p. 485).

The characteristics of rumors in Indian village can be classified into two points. The first is that rumors can be justified through current issues. With illiteracy widespread, and the regular channels of communication closed to them, for most people, rumors formed a fundamental mechanism for speaking out on issues. For example, during the Bombay Plague of 1896-1900, the British colonial government built hospitals in the village to provide medical treatments to those infected. The suspicion of the plague’s origin as well as the government’s reaction sent rumors among villagers flying. It was sometimes said that the plague did not exist at all but had been invented to enable low paid government servants to plunder the people at will, or that doctors were deliberately spreading the plague to improve their business. “Underlying almost all the rumors was an assumption of British self-interest and spite, a readiness to victimize and sacrifice Indians for the preservation of British power” (Arnold, 1987, p. 76). Some of the rumors voiced a suspicion not only of the British but also of those Indians who appeared to be their agents and allies. Another example makes it more clear

about the way peasants interpreted the movement in their own terms, translating the grand, remote and irrelevant national movement into their own ordinary life experience: Mahatma Gandhi gave a call for a no-tax campaign, while peasants transformed the no-tax campaign into a no-rent movement (Das, 1982, p. 71), and some peasants insisted that they will not pay more than eight annas a bigha as rent for their landlords. Therefore, it can be concluded that though deriving their legitimacy from the supposed orders of Gandhi, peasant actions in such cases were framed in terms of what was popularly regarded to be just, fair and possible.

The second is that rumors are closely related to the native culture and religion. It is undeniable that Indians’ deeply rooted religious beliefs are convenient to be exploited by rulers to serve their own needs. “Many of these rumors were very consciously spread by the local leaders, who took advantage of Gandhi’s charismatic appeal to give additional impetus to the agitation” (Amin, 1984, p. 6). However, evidence suggests that no authorized version of the Mahatma could have been handed down to the peasants who had a distinctly independent interpretation of their own (7). Gandhi evoked rather the mood of renunciation, austerity and sacrifice: die giving-up of fashionable garments and the prospect of comfortable jobs through official education, going to jail, unflinchingly facing lathis and bullets without retaliation, die ritual of fasts so deeply ingrained in Hindu tradition (Sarkar, 1984, p. 314).

In conclusion, rumor is a way for peasants to participate in the nation’s political practice. Without the skills of literacy, people were not only denied the possibility of using a range of media to express themselves, but their future preservation as subjects in history was threatened by their inability to commit memory and reflection to writing, therefore, it is necessary for us to listen attentively to the resonances of their spoken thoughts which endured in the form of rumors.

Decoding the Political Functions of Rumor through Four Novels

During the Indian National Movement: *The Village and Kanthapura*

Taking the British colonial rule as its historical background, *The Village* presents how the villagers understand the First World War and their own situation when the British army conscripted sepoys among them to the European battlefield. In the novel, the first rumor begins with an oracle. Hearing her husband whispered in the struggle of his life against death that he saw “the end of the world, the coming of the reign of darkness” (234), Gujri goes to the old Pandit and asks him whether her husband’s “prophecy” according with the spiritual sphere of the stars. “The Kaliyug has come, mother,” the priest said, taking the ring away from Gujri’s hand. “Youth will not respect age any more. Brother will not come to the aid of brother, and men will fight with swords in their hands. And there will be a great flood of fire arising from Vilayat, which will sweep over the whole world” (235). Gujri and the other worshippers who are near the shrine are frightened by the portents and go to tell the words of the prophecy to their relations. These awestruck listeners in their turn add their saliva to the oracle when they talk about it in the bazaar, letting their brooding imaginations work up the news into a wild, stirring rumour (235).

The villagers have various speculations about the war. Some regard it as another *Mahabharata*, because the “Angrezi Badshah was a cousin of the Badshah of Girmany, just as the Pandus were cousins of the Kurus” (251). The principles of light and darkness, right and wrong, are arrayed on opposite sides, fighting for supremacy, and all the powerful kingdoms within reach are drawn into the struggle as in the old days of the great war of Kurukshetra. Some draw an analogy between Father Annandale, who converts the lower castes like sweepers and leather workers to Christianity, with “German Badshah”, who are “in alliance with the Sultan of Turkey to spread

the religion of Islam in this world” (251); while others think that German Badshah would come and conquer Aryavarta to free India from slavery and spread the faith of the Vedas² (252). It can be seen that the villagers understand current issues in terms of their own mindset which integrates native culture and religion. Qiu Yonghui, a researcher at the Center for South Asian Studies, considers Hinduism “as a historical existence with unruly resilience”. In her view, Hinduism is a way of life rather than a theological system, and there is no clear line between the sacred and the secular (Qiu, 2012, p. 34-35).

Under such conditions, religion is often used by the ruling class as a political tool to initiate popular movements. Gandhi even said that “Politics loses its meaning when it is separated from religion”. (Chen, 2015, p. 2) He took advantage of Hinduism to unite subalterns with nationalists in the Nonviolent non-cooperation movements, taking them as an object of the Congress Party’s strategies, to be acted upon and controlled. Nevertheless, as the novel shows us through rumors, subalterns have their own ethics, which they, as active readers, learn from the religious texts and epics. They probably understand the good and evil according to who is in alliance with their religion, but they also have their positive understanding of the religious doctrines. Hinduism – Louis Althusser’s Ideological State Apparatus – teaches them to endure the sufferance, because “you have got what you have deserved through your Karma – your words, your thoughts, and your deeds” (Ghose, 2017, p. 43), but peasant subalterns still aspire for a better life because of their self-consciousness, their standards of judgment and established beliefs. The slightest glimmer of hope can ignite their passion.

In another novel *Kanthapura*, “Salt March” led by Gandhi was in full swing. In the small South Indian village Kanthapur, the villagers are accustomed to listening to old Ramakrishnayya, the very learned father of Rangamma, who reads

² The religious texts constitute the oldest layer of Sanskrit literature and the oldest scriptures of Hinduism.

out the Sankara-Vijaya day after day. And they go home to sleep, with the god's face framed within their eyes (41). Gandhi's story is told like this at religious gatherings. In a creative adaptation of the epic *Ramayana*, the storyteller weaves Gandhi's previous existence into a conversation between Brahma and Valmiki. He compares Gandhi to one of the avatars of Siva, who descends to the world to drive away "men coming from across the seas and the oceans to trample on our wisdom and to spit on virtue itself. They have come to bind us and to whip us, to make our women die milkless and our men die ignorant" (45), to liberate the wretched of the earth. And the imagination of what kind of life that Gandhi will bring to people is also told in the form of the Indian epic: "you put your eyes to a great tube and see another world with sun and moon and stars, all bright and floating in the diamond dust of God – in that country there were women who worked like men, night and day; men and women who worked night and day, and when they felt tired, they went and spent their holiday in a palace – no money for the railway, no money for the palace—and when the women were going to have a child, they had two months' and three months' holiday, and when the children were still young they were given milk by the Government, and when they were grown up they were sent free to school, and when they grew older still they went to the universities free, too." (68)

This pantisocracy where all men are equal – and there were neither the rich nor the poor – is actually far from what Gandhi conceived. Gandhi gave his ethical preaching in the name of God: truth is God, and the only means of truth is non-violence. In other words, because love is human nature, the principles of truth are the principles of love. He opposed untouchability as incompatible with the principle of non-violence and called it a stain of Hinduism. However, as the leader of the Congress Party, he was obliged to unite the country, which made his proposition full of compromise. The Zamindar system³ was

³ A zamindar in the Indian subcontinent was an autonomous or semi-autonomous ruler of a province. The term itself came into use during the reign of Mughals and later the British had begun using it as a

the source of the heavy burden on the farmers, but Zamindars, as the rich and powerful bourgeois, make it possible for the Congress Party to advance the nationalist movement. Therefore, in the face of the conflict between peasants and Zamindars, Gandhi advocated with an idealist attitude that "it is not contemplated that at any stages of non-cooperation we would seek to deprive the zamindars of their rent. The Kisan movement must be confined to the improvement of the status of the Kisans and the betterment of the relations between the zamindars and them". (Gandhi, 1921, p. 153) The zamindars will remove the difficulties of the peasants. Their managers are Congressmen. So they will definitely help the poor (Swami, 1952, p. 426). While the nationalist leadership sought to mobilize the peasantry as an anti-colonial force in its project of establishing a nation-state, it was ever distrustful of the consequences of agitational politics among the peasants, suspicious of their supposed ignorance and back-ward consciousness, "careful to keep their participation limited to the forms of bourgeois representative politics in which peasants would be regarded as a part of the nation but distanced from the institutions of the state." (Chatterjee, 1993, p. 86)

However, the peasants' political consciousness is actually reflected in their "ignorance" – their utopian fantasy – and misrecognition. The subalterns consider themselves as constructors of utopia, intend to "build a thousand pillared temple, a temple more firm than any that hath yet been built, and each one of you be ye pillars in it, and when the temple is built, stone by stone, and man by man, and the bell hung to the roof and the eagle-tower shaped and planted...India then will live in a temple of our making." (178) India will benefit from their joint resistance. From mouth to mouth, women, Dalits and coolies join together spontaneously through rumors and misrecognition. They go on strike, and refuse to pay taxes to the white chief. Women even acquaint themselves with the

native synonym for "estate". The term means land owner in Persian. Typically hereditary, from whom they reserved the right to collect tax on behalf of imperial courts or for military purposes.

imagination of the scene where “the policemen are beating” them: “we see them rise and become bigger and bigger in the sunshine, and we feel the lathis bang on us...” (182). In this way, when they actually meet the policemen, they find their lathis are “smaller than they had imagined, and their shoes have less nails” (182). It is in the effort of actively participating in the construction of utopia that subalterns no longer passively suffer from exploitation; rather, they construct their self-worth and subjective consciousness, to realize their “Brechtian forms of class struggle.”

Modernization after the Independence of India: *A Suitable Boy* and *Cradle of the Clouds*

A Suitable Boy takes India’s first general election, which came five years after the Congress Party was in power as its background. Zamindari Abolition Bill has just been legislated, but it didn’t cause serious conflict within the party of which Zamindars were the critical component, because the Bill still had loopholes that could be taken advantage of. Huge numbers of landlords “wisely” subdivided the lands of the family among the various members, and branded them as owner-cultivators, because large individual landholdings looked too suspicious, while asking the patwari to falsify the records, turning sharecroppers and rent-paying tenants, who sharecropped the field for more than five years without a break, and should be subdivided the piece of land according to the new law, to “hired employees who were rotated from field to field” (628).

Under such conditions, Nawab, who is identified as one of the largest landlords of the area, recommends his servant Waris to participate in the local elections as Independent, to help his friend, the Congressman Kapoor, to win the constituencies. Nevertheless, everything changes after Kapoor’s son Maan stabs his friend, Nawab’s son Firoz due to a personal affair. Gossip about Kapoor’s son and the Nawab continued to be exchanged at the small barber’s shop, in the vegetable market, over an evening hookah in a village courtyard, and wherever people met and talked (1401). According to the

political scientist James C. Scott, gossip, “the second cousin of rumor” (144) is mainly about the stories targeted at destroying one’s reputation. Most gossip is a discourse about social rules that have been violated. The purpose is to punish, chastise, or perhaps even drive out the offender. Bitter criticism via gossip is also used routinely by those at the bottom of the caste system to destroy the reputation of their high-caste superiors (Scott, 1990, p. 143). Kapoor and Nawab, one is the highly respected Minister of Revenue, another is one of the largest landlords, yet people can deconstruct their authority through gossip, disclosing their identity as self-interested politicians, to realize the subalterns’ micro-resistance.

What’s more, Waris utilizes rumors to give his opponent Kapoor a fatal blow. On the day before the election, when it would be too late for any effective refutation, appeared a small handbill in Urdu, printed in the thousands on flimsy pink paper. It appeared to have no author. There was no printer’s name at the bottom. It announced that Firoz had died the previous night, and called upon all faithful people, in his grieving father’s name, to cast their vote in such a way as to express their indignation against the author of this great misfortune (1403). This handbill flier traveling on the wind, found its way to almost every village in the constituency. In *The Village* and *Kanthapura*, we can see that rumors are originated from people’s imaginative interpretation of oracles, and it spreads by people in the bazaar and religious gatherings. In contrast, in *A Suitable Boy*, rumors have a concrete transmitter, Waris, and a new mode of transmission, namely, the printed handbill. As a servant, Waris should have been one of the underprivileged, a pawn thrust into the political arena; yet he, through his identity as a transmitter of rumors, unites the moral power – their sympathy for the victim and indignation for the murderer – of the villagers, infuses their values and consciousness to the political struggle. The morality of villagers can be translated as their belief in dharma, which, in Indian religions, represents behaviors that are considered to be in accord with Rta, the order that makes life and universe possible. It includes duties, rights, laws,

conduct, virtues and “right way of living”. (The Columbia Encyclopedia) Peasants may not understand the political game, and cannot predict which party will bring them a better life, but they can make their choice according to their own rules. From Waris, we can see the potential of a successful organizer of peasants’ movements. He knows the best way to stir up the masses, to spread rumors in the fastest way, that is, to imbue rumors with new strength by putting them into print. In his study of rural panic in revolutionary France, French historian Lefebvre observes that it seems unlikely that printing could have changed the character of these rumours to any significant degree; it merely increased their effectiveness as oral and unauthored speech. Moreover, people believed the rumors not out of any unquestioning trust in the printings, but because they accorded with existing beliefs about marvels and miracles, about right and wrong. (Lefebvre, 1973, p. 74) The same is true for the Indian peasants, who believe the rumors because of their pre-existing beliefs, their dharma.

The spread of governmental technologies in India in the last three decades, as a result of the deepening reach of the developmental state under conditions of electoral democracy, has meant that the state is no longer an external entity to the peasant community. Governmental agencies distributing education, health services, food, roadways, water, electricity, agricultural technology, emergency relief and dozens of other welfare services have penetrated deep into the interior of everyday peasant life. (Chatterjee, 2010, p. 193) As for peasants, who have lived in village for generations and are rooted in local culture and customs, it is not easy for them to accept innovation. Generally, they might be branded as backward, stubborn and conservative, yet the fact that their refusal is closely related to the unreasonable policy of the government is ignored.

In *Cradle of the Clouds*, we can see that some new laws about religious endowments and charitable institutions, the Rani Surabala’s Endowment were expected to pay an Entertainment Tax or some such impost. And the Trustees declared that the available funds did not permit them to

pay the new tax and entertain the master-potters and image-makers at the same time (148), so the general invitation to the master-potters and image-makers of West Bengal to the annual fair can not be issued in the usual way (147). The government destroys the local cultural festivals of villagers by increasing taxes, which makes them regard the government’s intervention in rural life as an ominous omen. Consequently, when politicians advertise “free and compulsory higher education for all”, the villagers sneer at it, considering it as the government’s another strategy to raise their taxes. It does not rain in the village for months and no food can be grown. As the price of the food and grain soared higher and higher, the villagers become more and more convinced that the rain is being held up by the machinations of a rascally-minded grain merchant (49), who probably forces the clouds to change their course by means of the wireless waves (36). Villagers see things in mythological patterns, mystifying the unknown, such as wireless waves. They are adept in imagining that exploiters are the incarnations of the evil forces beyond their control, and they are justified to fight against the evil forces through the moral law; hence the seeds of resistance are planted.

Panic among the villagers peaked when government officials came to take a census. There comes a sudden flood of forms from all sides: the District Boards, the offices of the Sub-Registrars, the Police Stations, the local Food Offices, the Provincial Home Affairs Department, the Central Publicity Office, etc. “All were asking for more or less the same information: statistical data concerning the inhabitants of the Blue Hills, their occupation, their domestic animals, their property” (155). Rumors about taxes stir up again, people wonder that “Do they want to tax our goats? Why do they want to know how many sheep we have?” (156) These rumors represent the undercurrents of popular mentalités. For they are the utterances of a people sharing common preoccupations about the system of taxation, which “thrust them into ambiguous situations where their life and livelihood seemed under attack”.(Yang, 1987, p. 500) Villagers are not

convinced that modern technology will improve their life quality; instead, they care about where they will be after the power plant and dam are built. Their fear is the spark that ignites the rebellion when some communists call on the villagers to resist the dam construction. They “love their scarlet earth and their cerulean hills with an intensity rarely known elsewhere.” (207) They are wedded to the soil where they are born. They are rooted in their native ground. Rumors are not based on superstition, stupidity and backwardness, but on peasant consciousness rooted in the land, their concern for worldly life and imaginative construction of culture.

Through rumors, the villagers find the capacity to speak in a common voice, and they try to make it loud enough to be heard by their superordinates. It can be seen that even though illiterate peasants are void of knowledge about complex political struggles, they still have their own ways, such as rumor, which is characterized by a sense of immediacy, continuity and participation, to make their responses in a micro level to the current political activities. Through creative interpretation of government policies and their life events, peasants exert their influence positively on the country’s political situation. As seen in the novel, it is not so much the Communists’ mobilization of the peasants as the peasants’ own selection of the Communist Party. A single spark can finally start a prairie fire.

Conclusion

The rumors reflecting an upsurge of suspicion, fear and anger may represent a popular tactical wisdom developed in conscious response to the political constraints realistically faced. Spontaneity, anonymity, and a lack of formal organization become enabling modes of protest rather than a reflection of the slender political talents of popular classes (Scott, 1990, p.151). The analysis of four novels, *The Village*, *Kantabapura*, *Cradle of the Clouds* and *A Suitable Boy* makes it clear that rumor makes the peasant subalterns the subject of history with their own distinctive forms of consciousness and making sense of and acting upon the world on its own

terms. The cultural apparatus of signs and meanings – the language, in the broadest sense – available to a peasant consciousness, far from being narrow and inflexible, is capable of “a vast range of transformations to enable it to understand, and to act within, varying contexts, both of subordination and of resistance.” (Chatterjee, 1993, p. 164)

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